

Report: Indo-Swiss Conference on Pharmacogenomics: special focus on Onco-Cardio Pharmacogenomics in Precision Medicine

Compiled by:

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The domains of oncology and cardiology have gained significant attention with the advent of precision medicine, especially in the realm of recent advances in pharmacogenomics. As cancer treatments advance, particularly with the use of targeted therapies, immune checkpoint inhibitors, and novel chemotherapeutic molecules, tremendous progress has been made in terms of treatment efficacy part. However, concerns on addressing adverse drug reactions or unwanted effects persist. These adverse effects sometimes compromise the efficacy of treatment but also affect patients' quality of life and survival outcomes. The integration of pharmacogenomics into clinical practice offers the potential to optimize therapeutic efficacy while minimizing adverse effects (PMID: 38490995). Genetic variations in drug-metabolizing enzymes, transporters, and molecular targets can significantly alter drug pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics. For example, polymorphisms in genes such as *CYP2D6*, *DPYD*, *CYP2C9* and *VKORC1* have been associated with individualized responses to chemotherapy and anticoagulants. Such personalized care has been touted to hold promise in curbing toxicities associated with medications, enhancing the outcome of therapy, and saving resources on health care.

Despite the promise, the clinical application of onco-cardio pharmacogenomics is hindered by limited genetic testing infrastructure, variability in guidelines, and ethical considerations about the use of genetic data. This gap can be filled through interdisciplinary collaboration between oncologists, cardiologists, geneticists, and pharmacologists, coupled with robust clinical trials to validate genetic markers and develop standardized protocols. Moreover, continued education is an essential part of implementing pharmacogenetic testing in clinic. This report covers the proceedings of the recent Indo-Swiss Conference on Pharmacogenomics (ISSCP) with specific focus on oncology and cardiology. This conference was held at Amrita School of Pharmacy and Amrita Institute of Medical Sciences, Kochi, India from 28th -30th November 2024. The conference received support from Leading House South Asia and Iran of ZHAW International office and CANSEARCH foundation from Switzerland. The event is also supported by SERB, India. CANSEARCH research platform of paediatric oncology and haematology of University of Geneva, Clinical pharmacology division of University of Geneva, Department of Medical Oncology at Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education and Research (JIPMER) and Amrita School of Pharmacy jointly organized the event. This is a 4th event of its kind in the series of Indo-Swiss collaborative continued education programs in the domain of pharmacogenomics (PMIDs: 33305611, 36786192, 38009368). Three parallel pre-conference workshops were conducted on 28th November 2024. Workshops objectives, schedules and relevant learning material is detailed in **Annexure 1**.

Among the 182 participants have been registered for the conference with major participation from PharmD program residents in training (70.7 %). Conference delegates also had opportunity to share their research projects in the domain with audience in the form of e-posters and oral presentations. The conference program, speaker abstracts, biographies and research abstracts of oral and poster presentations are provided in conference souvenir available as **Annexure 2**.

Conference was inaugurated on 29th with a warm welcome to delegates, esteemed dignitaries, and speakers from diverse fields. The inaugural address, delivered by Dr Narmada MP, Head, Department of Pharmacy Practice, highlighted the significance of Indo Swiss Conference in Pharmacogenomics in Onco Cardio Pharmacogenomics. The presidential and keynote address was delivered by Dr. Shanti Kumar Nair, Dean, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham and Dr. Sabitha M, Principal, Amrita School of Pharmacy, respectively. The ceremonial lamp lighting symbolized the enlightenment and knowledge-sharing anticipated during the sessions. The event set an inspiring tone, fostering discussions and collaborations, aimed at addressing challenges and advancing innovation in the health sciences.

In this report, we highlight brief excerpts from each of the talk in the order of the scientific schedule.

First talk of the conference. **Dr. Ambily Sivadas** was on "**Ethnic Differences in Pharmacogenomic Variant Distribution: Possible Impacts on Population-Specific Outcomes in Cardiology and Oncology.**" Dr. Sivadas highlighted the significant impact of ethnic differences in pharmacogenomic variants on drug efficacy and toxicity, emphasizing the need for precision medicine tailored to population-specific genetic profiles. In oncology, genetic polymorphisms in enzymes such as *CYP2D6*, *UGT1A1*, and *TPMT* influence the metabolism of drugs like tamoxifen, irinotecan, and thiopurines, leading to varied therapeutic outcomes across ethnic groups. Similarly, in cardiology, variants in *VKORC1*, *CYP2C9*, and *SLCO1B1* affect responses to warfarin, statins, and clopidogrel. These findings underscore the importance of integrating diverse genetic data into clinical practice to optimize treatments, reduce adverse events, and address disparities in underrepresented populations. Dr. Sivadas emphasized the need to understand the utilization patterns of pharmacogenomic-guided drugs in Indian healthcare settings, prioritize their clinical implementation, and improve patient outcomes through evidence-based guidelines.

Following, Dr. Vinod Scaria spoke on "**Challenges and Solutions in Communicating Pharmacogenomic Results to Clinicians and End Users: Experiences from India.**" Phenotype concordance with pharmacogenomics includes incidental genetic testing without clear clinical referrals, leading to inconsistent outcomes. Variability in terminology also complicates the interpretation of test results. To address these issues, standardized functional terms introduced by the Clinical Pharmacogenetics Implementation Consortium (CPIC) and the 2022 guidelines from the American College of Medical Genetics (ACMG) have improved clarity in pharmacogenomic reporting. Pharmacogenetic counselling is crucial for bridging the gap between genetic testing and clinical application, requiring specialized expertise to guide patients. Advances such as lower costs of genetic testing, integration with electronic health records (EHRs), and the use of artificial intelligence (AI) for data analysis are making precision medicine more accessible. Expanding pharmacogenomics into routine care can improve drug efficacy and reduce adverse drug reactions (ADRs).

Third talk by **Dr. Hisham Ahamed** highlighted the challenges in cardiology medication and the potential solutions offered by pharmacogenomics. Pharmacogenomics has emerged as a valuable tool in customizing treatment plans based on a patient's genetic profile, enabling predictions of how individuals metabolize and respond to cardiovascular drugs such as warfarin, clopidogrel, beta-blockers, and statins. Genetic variations in enzymes like *CYP2C9* and *VKORC1* can influence warfarin metabolism, requiring dosage adjustments to avoid complications like bleeding or clotting. Similarly, genetic testing for variants in genes like *SLCO1B1* can help identify patients at risk of statin-induced myopathy. By tailoring medication choices and dosages to a person's genetic makeup, pharmacogenomics reduces adverse drug reactions, enhances drug efficacy, and improves therapeutic outcomes. This precision approach is particularly valuable in managing complex cardiovascular conditions such as hypertension, heart failure, and arrhythmias, where standard treatment strategies often fall short. Integrating pharmacogenomics into routine cardiology practice has the potential to enhance patient safety, optimize treatment, and significantly improve cardiovascular care.

Following, **Dr. Sheetal K** shared her experience on "**Implementation of pharmacogenetic testing for oral anticoagulant dosing in a tertiary care hospital setting in Western India**". She highlighted how, she and her team have successfully integrated *CYP2C9* and *VKORC1* gene testing into clinical workflows for tailoring oral anticoagulant

therapy in a tertiary care hospital in Western India. Data from over 500 patients demonstrated that genotype-guided dosing significantly reduced adverse drug reactions, particularly bleeding complications, and improved therapeutic outcomes compared to conventional dosing strategies. Despite challenges such as cost constraints, clinician acceptance, and patient education, the implementation proved feasible and effective in a resource-limited setting. The findings underscore the potential of pharmacogenetic-guided anticoagulation therapy to enhance patient safety and optimize treatment outcomes, promoting the broader adoption of precision medicine in India's healthcare system.

Dr. Priyadharsini Rajendran added insights on Precision Cardiology: Harnessing pharmacogenomics for enhanced efficacy and patient safety with anti-platelet therapy. She emphasized the critical role of pharmacogenomics in optimizing antiplatelet therapy, particularly for drugs like **clopidogrel, prasugrel, and ticagrelor**. She highlighted how genetic variations influence the efficacy and safety of these medications, paving the way for personalized treatment plans in cardiology. Pharmacogenomic testing, specifically for *CYP2C19* genotypes, plays a crucial role in optimizing antiplatelet therapy. By tailoring treatment to a patient's genetic profile, clinicians can enhance drug efficacy, reduce adverse cardiovascular events, and improve overall patient outcomes. Implementing these guidelines ensures safer and more effective precision cardiology practices.

Following, **Prof. Pierre Fontana's shared his team's research project results during his talk on "Circulating MicroRNA as a Biomarker for Platelet Reactivity – A New Tool to Tailor Antithrombotic Therapy"**. He delivered an insightful presentation on the potential role of microRNAs (miRNAs) as biomarkers for platelet reactivity. This innovative research focuses on the regulatory role of miRNAs in platelet functions and their application in optimizing antithrombotic therapy. The findings underscore the transformative potential of miRNAs in cardiovascular medicine. By serving as biomarkers for platelet reactivity and thrombin generation, miRNAs could guide the development of precision medicine approaches for managing cardiovascular patients. This research represents a significant step forward in personalizing antithrombotic therapy, improving patient outcomes, and addressing a critical clinical challenge.

Next talk by Dr. Youssef Daali introduced "Physiologically based pharmacokinetic modelling (PBPK) concepts and its implications in personalized medicine practice in cardiology. Case studies on drug-drug interactions". He highlighted that the traditional "one-size-fits-all" approach has been replaced by precision medicine, where therapies are tailored to minimize side effects and optimize efficacy. Large interindividual variability in treatment response, influenced by genetic and environmental factors, underscores the need for personalized approaches. Pharmacokinetics (PK) variability, driven by genetic polymorphisms, drug-drug interactions (DDIs), and diseases, plays a critical role in this context. Metabolic enzymes, including phase I and II enzymes, and transporters are pivotal contributors to PK variability. Tools such as therapeutic drug monitoring, population pharmacokinetics (POPPK), and PBPK modelling are instrumental in addressing this variability and optimizing therapy. PBPK has emerged as a promising method in clinical practice, requiring validated models, comprehensive drug databases, and diverse patient scenarios to enhance the Model-Informed Precision Dosing (MIPD) approach. DDIs are of significant concern due to their high prevalence in patients with multiple morbid conditions and their potential to cause severe clinical outcomes, often resulting in hospitalizations.

Further, **Dr. Surulivel Rajan M provided insights on "Population Structure Differences: Opportunities for Personalized Dosing Using Population Modelling Case Studies."** He highlighted the potential of population pharmacokinetics or pharmacometrics to study sources and correlates of variability in drug concentrations among target patient populations. This approach incorporates patient-specific covariates such as biochemical markers, demographic characteristics, drug- and disease-related information, and genotypes that influence drug pharmacokinetics. By accounting for residual unexplained variability and inter-occasion variability, population pharmacokinetic models enable dose individualization and optimization. Personalized dosing is particularly critical for anticancer drugs to achieve optimal therapeutic outcomes with minimal adverse effects. In a study on Imatinib, population pharmacokinetic models were evaluated using data from their institute and Tata Memorial Cancer

Centre, Mumbai. These models facilitated the development of a simple dosing algorithm based on body weight, which demonstrated superior dose individualization compared to the current flat-dosing regimen. Dr. Rajan emphasized that integrating pharmacometric modelling with genetic markers holds immense potential for personalized therapy, particularly in oncology.

Following this, practicing oncologist **Dr Nikhil Krishna Haridas shared his thoughts on “Clinical implications of Pharmacogenomics in oncology practice-Case study on immune checkpoint inhibitors”**. His talk stressed about considering somatic variations in addition to the germline genetic variations. The intersection of pharmacogenomics and immunotherapy presents significant advancements in predicting and personalizing oncology treatment. Key genetic markers, such as microsatellite instability-high (MSI-H) and tumour mutational burden (TMB), play pivotal roles in identifying patients likely to benefit from immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs), with TMB (>10 mutations/mega base) serving as a tissue-agnostic biomarker for therapies like pembrolizumab. Additionally, biomarkers such as PD-L1 expression and PTEN status are crucial, as PTEN loss is associated with reduced CD8+ T-cell infiltration and resistance to ICIs. Pharmacogenomics also aids in managing immune-related adverse events (irAEs) by identifying genetic predispositions, such as HLA variations linked to toxicity, enabling early prediction and prevention. Despite challenges like the prohibitive cost of genetic testing and limited data, future directions include integrating multi-omics approaches, artificial intelligence, and machine learning for predictive modelling, discovering novel biomarkers, and enhancing pharmacogenomics education to optimize immunotherapy outcomes.

The concluding session of the first day of the conference featured a debate on the topic, "Are we there yet or it is just the beginning- implementation of pharmacogenomics in oncology?". Dr. Rekha Priyadarshini debated in favour of motion, while Dr. Gerard Marshall Raj presented opposing views. Moderated by Dr. Uppugunduri S. Chakradhar Rao, the session began with an acknowledgment of the barriers to implementing pharmacogenetic testing despite the high hopes following the completion of the Human Genome Project. Dr. Rekha highlighted cases such as neutropenia in paediatric acute lymphoblastic leukaemia receiving 6-mercaptopurine, which could have been avoided with pharmacogenetic testing, and pointed to its benefits in reducing adverse events, improving clinical outcomes, and lowering treatment costs. She emphasized that testing is a one-time requirement and presented the Taiwanese model, where nationwide testing for carbamazepine-induced Stevens–Johnson syndrome significantly reduced adverse events. In contrast, Dr. Gerard quoted the CDC’s statement about the limited clinical use of pharmacogenetic testing, attributing this to barriers such as ethnic bias in published data, lack of substantial evidence, cost, and educational and organizational challenges. He also questioned its practical efficacy, citing studies showing no significant difference between pharmacogenetic-guided and conventional dosing. Most participants voted for the motion supporting pharmacogenetic testing, with the percentage in favour increasing from 81% before the debate to 85% afterward. The debate underscored the importance of addressing barriers and gathering robust data to optimize the use of pharmacogenetic testing, particularly in resource-constrained settings.

Day 2 of the conference began with a talk by **Dr. Prasant Ganeshan on "Pharmacogenomics in Oncology: Applications in Practice and Opportunities in Research."** He emphasized that genomic variations in drug metabolism significantly influence the efficacy of various anticancer agents. Pharmacogenomics also plays a critical role in understanding genetic variations in tumours, enabling personalized cancer therapy. Key examples of metabolic variations include *TPMT* mutations affecting 6-mercaptopurine, *DPD* variations influencing fluorouracil and capecitabine, and *UGT1A1* polymorphisms impacting irinotecan bioavailability. This rapidly evolving field offers opportunities to uncover additional causes of variability in drug responses for both cytotoxic and targeted agents. Genome-wide association studies have advanced our understanding beyond single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)-based research. Targeted therapy, a major focus of oncology research over the past two decades, has driven the development of numerous novel drugs, significantly improving survival across various cancer types. The discussion following talk emphasized reluctance in undertaking of pharmacogenetic testing by clinicians citing reasons of lack of evidence in Indian population, however similar reluctance is not shown when it comes to somatic genetic testing despite lacking evidence form same ethnic population.

Following, Dr. Uppugunduri S. Chakradhara Rao introduced **CURRENT CPIC GUIDELINES** to the audience. Dr. Uppugunduri covered DPD testing 5 fluorouracil and *TPMT*, *NUDT15* genotyping and 6 mercaptopurine dosing guidelines. He highlighted the significance of the Clinical Pharmacogenetics Implementation Consortium (CPIC) guidelines in aiding clinicians to integrate pharmacogenetic information into treatment decisions. The CPIC guidelines are developed based on robust evidence and expert consensus. One notable success in pharmacogenetics is the *TPMT*, *NUDT15* and 6-mercaptopurine dosing guidelines, which optimizes therapy during the maintenance phase of paediatric acute lymphoblastic leukaemia. Genetic testing helps identify poor metabolizers of *TPMT* and people with also dysfunctional *NUDT15* enzyme, who are at higher risk of myelosuppression. In oncology, other significant examples include *UGT1A1* polymorphisms linked to irinotecan toxicity, *CYP2D6* polymorphisms influencing tamoxifen response, *DPYD* polymorphisms associated with 5-fluorouracil or capecitabine toxicity, and *KRAS* mutations impacting EGFR inhibitor efficacy. In cardiology, the *CYP2C9* genetic variants are critical for warfarin response, while *CYP2C19* variants affect clopidogrel response, *SLCO1B1* gene variants are linked to statin toxicity, and *PCSK9* variants guide the selection of *PCSK9* inhibitors. Dr. Rao emphasizes the importance of these guidelines, particularly in the context of their relevance to the Indian population.

Dr. Khalil Ben Hassine, then shared his research experience on “**INCORPORATION OF PHARMACOGENETIC INFORMATION INTO POPULATION PK MODELS FOR MODEL-INFORMED PRECISION DOSING: A CASE STUDY FROM ONCOLOGY**”. His research findings emphasized optimizing busulfan (Bu)-based conditioning chemotherapy using model informed precision dosing (MIPD) and pharmacogenetics to improve therapeutic outcomes. A PopPK model for Bu, developed using clinical data from 302 paediatric patients and validated in 100 additional patients, incorporates patient-specific factors such as weight, age, *GSTA1* pharmacogenetic variations, and fludarabine co-administration. The model predicted therapeutic Bu exposures for 81% of patients using a priori dosing and is being evaluated in a randomized multicentre study (Bugenes01, NCT04822532) to assess the clinical benefits of pharmacogenetic-based dosing. Simulations demonstrated that Bayesian estimation using minimal sampling schedules accurately predicted Bu exposure, although therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) over two dosing days was critical for precise cumulative exposure. The model was integrated into user-friendly MIPD software, supporting a priori and Bayesian dosing recommendations. This approach optimizes Bu exposure, reducing toxicity and relapse risks, and exemplifies the integration of precision medicine into routine HSCT practice.

Dr Sachin David delivered a talk on PHARMACOGENOMICS TESTING IN ONCOLOGY – AMRITA EXPERIENCE. He discussed the role of pharmacogenomics in oncology, emphasizing its potential to address inter-individual variability in drug response and improve treatment outcomes. Genetic variations significantly impact drug efficacy and safety, prompting a shift from the “one drug fits all” approach to personalized medicine. At Amrita Hospital, genes like **DPYD**, **CYP2C9**, **CYP2C19**, **TPMT**, **VKORC**, and **MTHFR** are routinely studied for pharmacogenomic applications. For instance, *DPYD* mutations, which affect fluorouracil metabolism, were found in 12.5% of patients with gastrointestinal, breast, and head and neck cancers, with variants such as **c.496A>G** being particularly prevalent in South Asians and linked to severe adverse reactions. Additionally, *CYP2C19* genotyping identifies normal and intermediate metabolizers, aiding drug selection and dosage. *TPMT* mutations, which affect thiopurine metabolism, are highly polymorphic, and incorporating **NUDT15** testing is recommended for Asian populations to address population-specific variations in drug-induced toxicity. These findings highlight the importance of population-based pharmacogenomic studies, especially in ethnically diverse regions like India. Despite previous resource constraints, integrating pharmacogenomics into clinical practice can optimize drug therapy, prevent adverse effects, and improve patients' quality of life.

This talk was followed by a panel discussion Tools (e.g. Pharmacogenomics, Pharmacometrics, TDM) with implications of bringing in precision for optimized therapy in oncology Moderator: Dr, Uppugunduri S. Panellists: Dr.

Wesley, Dr. Rajan S, Dr. Khalil BH, Dr. Folefac Aminkeng, Dr. Sachin David. This discussion highlighted collaboration between interdisciplinary teams is essential for optimized therapy practice.

Then, **Dr. Folefac Aminkeng delivered a talk titled "Precision Health Pharmacogenomics Research and Clinical Implementation in Oncology: Current Status and Future Challenges with Specific Emphasis on Biological Molecules."** Pharmacogenomics (PGx) approach has already demonstrated significant clinical benefits, including identifying patients at high risk of severe adverse drug reactions and therapeutic failure, thereby optimizing treatment outcomes. However, challenges such as high costs, complex data interpretation, emerging resistance mechanisms, and regulatory hurdles need to be addressed for broader clinical adoption and global impact. Dr. Aminkeng highlighted the substantial progress made in integrating PGx into oncology and emphasized the need for continued efforts to overcome these challenges to enhance precision health initiatives. Dr. Aminkeng also shared the results from his research work on biological molecules and associated toxicities, and possible genetic predictors.

This was followed by a brief session on **Perspectives of oncologist, clinical pharmacologist, test providers, Basic Researcher on pharmacogenomic testing in oncology (Oncologist: Dr. Nikhil; Clinical Pharmacologist: Dr.G. Lakshmi, Test providers: Dr. Sahana S (Indus Health).** Pharmacogenomic testing in oncology presents valuable perspectives from diverse professionals, emphasizing its potential to enhance precision medicine. Dr. Lakshmi, a clinical pharmacologist, underscored the importance of genetic variant analysis, particularly DPYD testing, for predicting drug metabolism and responses. She advocated a stepwise approach involving genotype analysis and metabolite evaluation when direct phenotypic assessment is unavailable. Dr. Lakshmi also highlighted the integration of Pharmacoeconomics into pharmacogenomic research, the ethical concerns of pre-emptive screening, and the critical need for informed consent in countries with limited data privacy awareness. Dr. Nikhil, an oncologist, emphasized the practical application of pharmacogenomic testing, such as detecting germline EGFR mutations, and the necessity of counselling patients to prepare them for the outcomes of genetic testing. He highlighted cost-effectiveness, the importance of comprehensive databases, and the challenges of translating genetic data into actionable clinical decisions. Dr. Sahana, a test provider, addressed the need for ethnic-specific data in pharmacogenomic guidelines and emphasized the importance of public awareness to increase adoption. Across these perspectives, key challenges include cost, ethical considerations, privacy, and data sharing, while collaboration and patient-centred approaches are essential for successful implementation in healthcare.

Following, **Dr. Neeraj Sidharthan**, in his talk on "**Germline Genetic Testing in Haematological Malignancies: Scope for Contribution,**" highlighted the critical role of germline genetic testing in identifying inherited predispositions to haematological malignancies and its impact on personalized treatment and surveillance strategies. For instance, TPMT mutations, which affect thiopurine metabolism, can lead to severe myelosuppression when azathioprine is administered, but dose adjustments based on genetic testing can prevent such toxicities. Individuals with Down syndrome, predisposed to acute leukaemia due to genetic abnormalities, benefit from early genetic screening and tailored low-dose chemotherapy to minimize treatment-related side effects. Similarly, patients with Fanconi anaemia (FA), a condition marked by chromosomal instability, require germline testing to guide cancer surveillance and adjust pre-transplant conditioning, often reducing or omitting alkylating agents and radiation to minimize toxicity during hematopoietic stem cell transplantation. In telomeropathies such as dyskeratosis congenita, genetic testing informs the use of treatments like danazol, which slows telomere attrition, improves haematopoiesis, and reduces transfusion dependence, significantly improving patient outcomes. Overall, germline genetic testing facilitates personalized cancer monitoring, therapy adjustments, and toxicity reduction, underscoring its transformative potential in the management of haematological malignancies.

The conference session was concluded by concluding remarks by Dr. Uppugunduri and Dr. Youssef Daali, following distribution of best poster and oral prizes for the winners and vote of thanks by Dr. Prashant Chandra.

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Feedback on the conference is provided in **Annexure 3**.